

www.arseam.com
Impact Factor: 0.98

A STUDY OF PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN I.T. INDUSTRY

Prof. M. Mustafa

Dean

School of Management Science
Lingaya's University, Faridabad (HR)

Mohd. Mumshad

Assistant Professor

Department of Management Studies
Al-Falah University, Faridabad (HR)

ABSTRACT

Indian I.T. Industry has built a strong base throughout the world owing to its high standard of software technology, service quality and technical know-how to implement the software process. The demand of Indian I.T. Industry has grown very fast particularly in USA and Europe during the last decade due to effective implementation of software. And this has become possible because of effective utilization of skilled manpower. Performance Management System is a tool which is used to manage to executives. It gives a holistic approach to engage each and every employee in the organization to improve their performance as well as the organization continuously. It is a system that provides a platform to create the atmosphere of work culture where employees can perform efficiently. It is a tool which is used to enhance the skills of employees. It is used to motivate the employees so that they can work in the organization for a longer period of time. The paper discusses about the role of performance management systems in I.T. Industry.

Keywords: Performance Management System, Information Technology, Balanced Scorecard, Organizational objectives, departmental objectives, individual employee objectives

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction of Performance Management System:

Performance Management System has become a key component in the organization that ties the strategic issues with HR processes. This allows the organization to define an organizational performance plan that may work as a tool to bring all the critical elements together. A number of managerial skills are crucial for successful implementation of Performance Management System such as:

- a) Ability to get work done;
- b) Setting challenging goals for self and subordinates;
- c) Good communication skills;
- d) Technically competent;
- e) Team building spirit;
- f) Loyal and supportive to management and employees;
- g) Have high values in life;
- h) Positive bent of mind;
- i) Commitment towards work.

Success or failure of Performance Management System in any organization depends on the following criteria:

- a) Organizational philosophies;
- b) Attitudes and skills of those responsible for its implementation;
- c) Acceptance, commitment and ownership of managers and employees;
- d) Procedural fairness and distinctive justice;
- e) Top management commitment and involvement;
- f) Adequacy of pay level or compensation package;

- g) Availability of resources, tools and skills of employees to do their job;
- h) Scope for managers to have the power to make decisions and plans on the basis of needs;
- i) Effectiveness of communications within management and employees;
- j) A culture of accountability and openness prevails;
- k) Financial requirements of the organization;
- l) Decentralization;
- m) Customer's pressure and quality assurance.

1.2 Overview of I.T. Industry:

Indian I.T. Industry has grown very fast due to effective designing and implementation of computer-based information systems, particularly software applications and computer hardware. These days, it has become clear that without information technology no any country in the world can march towards global competitiveness. In each and every sector, and even for healthy GDP, Defence capabilities, Information Technology has become mandatory. India has made a global value because of Information Technology Industry. Perception about India by the people of developed countries has changed owing to its booming I.T. industrial sector which has helped India to make its mark on the world map.

The contributions being made by the IT industry towards the country's GDP has led to a steady growth of the Indian economy. India's IT industry is regarded as a hub of innovators providing world class technology solutions across the globe. Various international organizations have set up their offices here in India like Google, Accenture etc. It has helped in changing Indian economy from agricultural based economy to a knowledge driven economy. IT sector has helped the domestic economy to integrate with the world economy. It has made significant impacts on the lives of many people. It has also helped people settled in far flung topographies to connect with the rest of the world. It has given birth to e-governance practices, as a result of which people get an easy access via e-health, e-education, e-ticketing etc. to the various governmental services.

1.3 Performance Management Systems in I.T. Industry:

According to Armstrong and Baron (1998), Performance Management System is a “strategic and integrated approach that increases the effectiveness of companies by improving the performance of the employees who work in the company and develop the team spirits.” Employee's individual goals are matched with the organizational goals that help to increase the productivity and profitability of the organization. The aim of performance management system is to develop individuals with the required commitment and competencies in order to achieve the organizational objectives. Frameworks of performance management systems are designed with the objective of improving both the individual and organizational performance by identifying performance requirements, by providing continuous feedback and assisting the employees in their career development. Performance management system focuses on goal clarity for making people do the right things in the right time. It also ensures that the organization as a system and its subsystems work together in an integrated mode for attaining optimum results.

There are certain components for an effective Performance management system. These include performance planning, performance analysis and review, rewarding good performance (annual increment), employee development plan and job design. Performance planning has to be done jointly by the appraisee and reviewer in the beginning of a performance session and during this period the employees decide upon the targets and key performance areas. Normally the appraisals are performed twice in a year. In this process, the appraisee first offers the self-appraisal forms and then final ratings are provided by the appraiser for the quantifiable and measurable achievements of the employee being appraised. Feedback and counseling is given a lot of importance in the performance management process. At this stage the employee receives an open and a very transparent feedback and along with this the training and development needs of the employee is also identified. The appraiser adopts all the possible steps to ensure that employee meets the expected outcomes for an organization through effective personal counseling and guidance, mentoring and representing the employee in training programs which develop the competencies and improve the overall productivity. Rewards and annual increment are vital components for work motivation of an employee. An employee is publicly recognized for

good performance and is rewarded. If the employee shows poor performance then again fresh set of goals are established for that employee and new deadline is provided for accomplishing those objectives. The employee is clearly communicated about the areas in which the employee is expected to improve and a stipulated deadline is also assigned within which the employee must show the improvement. Performance development plans are also jointly developed by the appraisee and the appraiser and is mutually approved. The performance management approach has become an indispensable tool in the hands of the corporate as it ensures that the people will uphold the corporate values and tread in the path of accomplishment of the ultimate corporate vision and mission. It is a forward looking process as it involves both the supervisor and also the employee in a process of joint planning and goal setting in the beginning of the year.

1.4 Balanced Scorecard – At a Glance:

- a) Balanced Scorecard is a tool which is used for performance management systems. It is more user friendly in I.T. Industry that helps to manage, evaluate and guide the performance of each and every employee. Balanced Scorecard is a tool which facilitates the employees to improve the performance and classify the targets in four perspectives – financial, customers, process and people.
- b) Importance of Balanced Scorecard:
 - Balanced Scorecard is a management system to articulate and communicate vision and strategy.
 - It is a cascade strategy to specify goals and targets.
 - Classify goals and targets into four perspectives – financial, customer, process and people.
 - It helps to identify cause and effect relationships between the goals and targets under the four perspectives i.e. financial, customers, process and people.
 - It helps to monitor and review the performance.
- c) Chart of Balanced Scorecard for Manager – HR:

Scorecard of Manager – HR									
Perspective	Strategic Objectives (KRA)	Performance Measure (KPI)	Weightage	Calibration					Achievement
				1	2	3	4	5	
Financial	Budget	Timely analysis of budget to monitor	10%						
Process	Annual increment	Compilation of increment data	10%						
	Trackers	Create Dash Board	10%						
	Job Design	Standardization of Job Designs	10%						
	SOPs	100% compliance of SOPs	10%						
Customer	Recruitment	Searching of cv on web portal as per recruitment plan	10%						
		To complete recruitment as agreed by HODs	20%						
People	Employee development	Develop employee for recruitment process	20%						

- d) Performance Ratings: Performance Appraisal of the employee is the core activity which forms the bedrock of the PMS. Briefly, the PMS actions are based on the outcome of the appraisal process which is based on 5-point rating scale, are as under.

Rating	Description	
5	Significantly exceeds expectations	Appraisee has performed as a model of excellence for his/her position. His performance is exemplary under challenging conditions and has surpassed all expectations in this KPI to a degree deserving special recognition.
4	Exceeds expectations	Appraisee has exceeded expectations from the role in this KPI. Appraisee has demonstrated good performance and overcome challenges on the job.
3	Meets expectations	Appraisee has demonstrated effectiveness in this KPI. He/she has made a strong contribution to the job through fully satisfactory performance in this area.
2	Partially meets expectations	Appraisee has generally met most expectations in this KPI. This was a satisfactory capability level with need for continued development.
1	Does not meet expectations	Appraisee has performed deficiencies that need improvement in order to meet the expectations fully from his/her position. Does not meet minimum job requirements. Performance is unacceptable.

- e) Performance Management Cycle: (1 April to 31 March of successive year)
- Performance Planning: - 1 April to 15 April
 - Organizational Goal Setting
 - Cascade to Departmental Goals
 - Cascade to Individual Goals
 - Mid-Term Review: - 15 Sept to 30 Sept
 - Tracking performance on a regular basis
 - Providing developmental feedback
 - Opportunity for course correction
 - Year-End Review: - 15 March to 30 March
 - Appraising actual performance against established goals
 - Normalization and Final Rating: - 15 March to 30 March
 - Normal distribution for equity
 - Linking performance to pay
 - Final Rating
 - Development Planning: - 15 March to 30 March
 - Identify developmental needs
 - Setting developmental goals
- f) PMS Process Step:
- Performance Planning:
 - Organizational goals to be communicated to all employees.
 - Developmental goals to be cascaded from organizational goals.
 - Individual goals to be cascaded from departmental goals and Reporting Manager's KRA/KPIs.
 - Joint discussion between Appraisee and Reporting Manager to set goals and targets for the year.
 - Mid-Term Review:
 - Mid-term review process to be introduced to review progress against goals and modify targets, if required.
 - No formal rating during Mid-Term Review, one-on-one qualitative and performance/developmental feedback session with Reporting Manager.

- Year-End Review:
 - Self assessment against achievement of KRA/KPIs and competencies.
 - Reporting Manager provides performance feedback and assessment on each KRA/KPIs.
 - Reporting Manager not to communicate rating at this stage.
 - Move to a 5-point rating scale.
- Normalization and Final Rating:
 - Normalization to happen within each department based on organizational performance.
 - Normalization curve to shift depending on organizational performance.
 - At this stage, final normalized rating would be shared with the employee by Reporting Manager.
- Development Planning:
 - Provide developmental feedback to the employee and set development goals for the role holder.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Performance management systems are powerful tool for change. They were used in the 1980s and 1990s to try to bring about change in public sector culture and ethos. People in the same job with the same experience expected and got the same pay and had roughly the same prospects of promotion. The shift towards a performance culture was a dramatic one. It was based on equity, rather than equality, and managed by means of performance. Since that meant being rewarded for what the employees did, it also required help and clear feedback on a regular basis from managers on individual performance. It required specific goals and targets to be set, with measurable success criteria such as key performance indicators, or key result areas. It required regular progress reviews and a meaningful annual appraisal. Data had to be collected on performance and that served as the basis for all decision making.

Craig Eric Schneir identified the problems typically encountered when attempting to improve performance, productivity, and quality through implementing performance management system. Organizations develop strategic plans that may call for new products or technologies. These plans must become operational in order to succeed. The goals and the vision are necessary, but rarely sufficient. They must be coupled with a performance management system that identifies what counts, helps measure it and holds people accountable for achieving it. Long run, institutionalized change occurs if key human resource management systems, such as appraisal, reward, selection, and training are affected. There is a weak relationship in many organizations between what is formally stated as important and what is known by employees and managers to count. Inconsistencies between performance and compensation are often painfully obvious. A recent study showed that less than one in three companies actually linked top executive rewards to corporate performance. In order to attain lasting change, performance must be identified and measured via performance management and rewarded and recognized via an effective recognition and reward system. A survey has indicated that top management must build the accountability required to allow change to occur. Consequences for performance- positive and negative- must be available. Many organizations have restricted or eliminated across-the-board pay increases. Monetary rewards are often scarce and other rewards are highly valued. With values and expectations, today's work force demands a broad view of rewards. Victor Y.Hanies(2004) published an article in Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences. According to him organizations increasingly view performance management as a key system that can promote and sustain initiatives such as speed to market, business performance expectations, feedback, and reward systems to people requirements, performance management may foster employee behaviors that are consistent with emerging business opportunities and the need for strategic and operational effectiveness.

Deming(1986) and Bowman, Scholtes(1994) argue, however, that the practice of performance management, including performance appraisal, is not compatible with the principles of quality management. Their main contention is that performance management is too focused on individual characteristics rather than on system

factors. In response to Deming's admonition, a number of scholars countered that traditional performance management practices could be customized to support quality.

In the survey conducted by Juran(1986), Walton(1989) it was found that the stronger the organizations emphasis on quality, the more prevalent will be the use of contextual work behavior performance criteria.

Blakburn&Rosen(1993) conducted a survey on a customer-centric organization and found out that the stronger the organizations emphasis on quality, the greater the focus on competencies within the performance management system. Performance management system components that are consistent with a quality emphasis will have a stronger positive influence on performance management effectiveness in organizations with a greater quality emphasis. A quality emphasis will have stronger positive influence on organizational performance when the strategic integration of human resource management is greater.

2.1 Components of Performance Management System

2.1.1 Performance Planning Performance planning is the first crucial component of any performance management process which forms the basis of performance appraisals. Performance planning is jointly done by the appraisee and also the reviewee in the beginning of a performance session. During this period, the employees decide upon the targets and the key performance areas which can be performed over a year within the performance budget, which is finalized after a mutual agreement between the reporting officer and the employee.

2.1.2 Performance Analysis and Review The analysis are normally done twice in a year in an organization in the form of mid reviews and annual reviews which is held in the end of the financial year. In this process, the appraisee first offers the self-filled up ratings in the self-appraisal form and also describes his/her achievements over a period of time in quantifiable terms. After the self-appraisal, the final ratings are provided by the appraiser for the quantifiable and measurable achievements of the employee being appraised. Feedback on the performance followed by personal counseling and performance facilitation: Feedback and counseling is given a lot of importance in the performance management process. This is the stage in which the employee acquires awareness from the appraiser about the areas of improvements and also information on whether the employee is contributing the expected levels of performance or not. The employee receives an open and a very transparent feedback and along with this the training and development needs of the employee is also identified. The appraiser adopts all the possible steps to ensure that the employee meets the expected outcomes for an organization through effective personal counseling and guidance, mentoring and representing the employee in training programs which develop the competencies and improve the overall productivity.

2.1.3 Reward/Annual Increment This is a very vital component as it will determine the work motivation of an employee. An employee is publicly recognized for good performance and is rewarded accordingly. This stage is very sensitive for an employee as this may have a direct influence on the self-esteem and achievement orientation. Any contributions duly recognized by an organization helps an employee in coping up with the failures successfully and satisfies the need for affection.

2.1.4 Performance Development Plan In this stage, fresh set of goals are established for an employee and new deadline is provided for accomplishing those objectives. The employee is clearly communicated about the areas in which the employee is expected to develop and a stipulated deadline is also assigned within which the employee must show the improvement. This plan is jointly developed by the appraisee and the appraiser and is mutually approved.

2.1.5 Potential Appraisal The competency which forms a basis for both lateral and vertical movement of employees cannot be measured easily. By implementing competency mapping and various assessment techniques, potential appraisal is performed for diversified improvement in skills. Potential appraisal provides crucial inputs for succession planning and job rotation. Performance management is an ongoing process of identifying, measuring and developing human performance in organizations. The data which is gathered by

systematic observations not only to measure current performance accurately but also to provide the necessary feedback information for changes that will improve future performance.

Guinn(1987) also proposes a three-step process: planning, managing and appraising. Torrington and Hall(1995) also proposed a model of three steps: planning, supporting and reviewing performance. Supporting performance is seen as a responsibility of the line manager who also has a particular part to play in reviewing performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Objectives:

- i) To study the Performance Management Systems in I.T. Industry;
- ii) To find out the level of executive satisfaction with respect to Performance Management Systems;
- iii) To give suggestion in order to make Performance Management System more effective.

3.2 Data Collection:

Data was collected with the help of self structured questionnaire . Total 90 questionnaires were sent through email to the Executives working in IT industry in Delhi & NCR. Out of which only 50 questionnaires were correctly filled and was used for data analysis. Since the data collection on such crucial topic i.e. performance management system has become a challenge these days; but somehow I have got the opportunity to get interacted with the executives in I.T. Industry and was able to collect data from them.

IV. EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Analysis and Findings:

Questions which were raised during interview with the management people in the organization are as under:

- a) Whether you correlate your individual contribution with the overall organizational growth?

55% respondents were strongly agreed about their individual contribution that correlated with the organizational overall growth. Similarly, 30% respondents were agreed with the same view. While 10% of the respondents were undecided and only 5% executives were disagreed with this view.

Thus, I can conclude that most of the executives feel very positive about the goal setting process in order to generate more profits for the organizational overall development.

- b) Whether there are any linkages between Performance Management System and Human Resource Management?

30% respondents were strongly agreed with the opinion while other 30% were agreed. 20% respondents were disagreed while rest 20% was strongly disagreed with this view.

Though majority of the executives were of the same view and their firm belief that there are strong linkages between performance management system and human resource management still some of them have different opinion.

My assumption is that management should focus on understanding of the subordinates on such topic so that they can get acquainted with the objectives of performance management system very well.

c) Do you have clarity about what you are supposed to achieve?

70% respondents were strongly agreed while 20% respondents were agreed that they have full clarity about what they are supposed to achieve.

In the said organization, work culture has been developed and due to which employee understands very well about the goal setting process. Whenever they feel any problem for setting goals, they take assistance from their superiors easily. It is a good indication in the organization.

d) Whether you assist your subordinates to decide their performance targets?

65% respondents were strongly agreed that they guide their subordinates to decide their performance targets, while 15% of them agreed with the same view. 5% respondents were undecided while rest 10% were disagreed and strongly disagreed with this view.

Thus, I can conclude that majority of the executives guide their subordinates in target setting process. It means there is an atmosphere of cooperation, coordination and mutual understanding within the organization which are mandatory for the development of any organization.

e) Do you agree that the performance analysis and review system in the organization is significant?

55% respondents were strongly agreed while 35% of them were agreed. Rest 10% respondents were disagreed with the opinion that the performance analysis and review system in the organization is significant. Thus, I can conclude that majority of the executives feel positive about the performance analysis and review system in the organization as significant. Their perception is that due to significant performance analysis and review system they achieve the target easily as they get corrective suggestions from superiors during their review meetings.

f) Do you think environment and relationship during review meetings open and cordial?

30% respondents were strongly agreed while 50% of them were agreed with the opinion that the environment and relationship during review meetings remain open and cordial. 10% respondents were undecided while other 10% were disagreed and strongly disagreed with the view.

Due to distinct work culture, it has become possible in the organization that there are openness during the review meetings which is mandatory for achieving the targets which are assigned to the individual employee in the organization.

g) Whether performance review meetings serve their purpose?

30% respondents were strongly agreed while 50% were agreed with the opinion that the performance review meetings serve their purpose. 5% respondents were undecided while rest 15% were disagreed and strongly disagreed with this view.

Thus, I can conclude that performance management system which is adopted in the organization serve the purpose because executives work with full enthusiasm and achieve the target which is rare in the present cut throat competitive era.

h) What is your perception about the assigned targets which are given in terms of no. are clearly demarcated?

20% respondents were strongly agreed while 35% were agreed with the view that the assigned targets which are given in terms of no. are clearly demarcated. 20% respondents were undecided and rest 25% respondents were disagreed and strongly disagreed with the view.

Thus, I can conclude that the targets which are assigned to the individual executive in terms of no. are clearly demarcated which are based on mutual agreement between appraiser and appraisee; but some are confused because they have no clarity on the issue.

i) Do you agree that capabilities of your subordinates match with their functions and responsibilities?

65% respondents were strongly agreed while 25% were agreed with the view that the capabilities of their subordinates match with their functions and responsibilities. 5% respondents were undecided while rest 10% respondents were disagreed and strongly disagreed with this view.

Thus, I can conclude that the work culture which is developed in the organization is based on mutual cooperation and trust between superiors and subordinates. This is the reason why whenever any subordinate face any kind of problem concerned superior cooperate him and try to solve the problem amicably. In this way capabilities of subordinates are being matched with their functions and responsibilities.

V. FINDINGS

- a. 85% respondents were agreed about their individual contributions that correlate with the organizational overall growth.
- b. 60% respondents were agreed with the opinion that there are strong linkages between performance management system and human resource management.
- c. 90% respondents were agreed that they have full clarity about what they are supposed to achieve. In the I.T. Industry, work cultures have been developed and due to which executives understand very well about the goal setting process.
- d. 80% respondents were agreed that they guide their subordinates to decide their own performance targets. It means there is an atmosphere of cooperation, coordination and mutual understanding within the I.T. Industry which are mandatory for the development of any organization.
- e. 90% respondents were agreed with the opinion that the performance analysis and review system in the organization is significant.
- f. 80% respondents were agreed with the opinion that the environment and relationship during review meetings remain open and cordial.
- g. 80% respondents were agreed with the opinion that the performance review meetings serve their purpose.
- h. 55% respondents were agreed with the view that the assigned targets which are given in terms of no. are clearly demarcated.
- i. 90% respondents were agreed with the view that the capabilities of their subordinates match with their functions and responsibilities.

VI. CONCLUSION

Majority of employees in I.T. Industry are well aware about the Performance Management Systems. The employees have a complete idea about the various aspects of performance evaluation in the organization except those elements which are kept confidential.

When mid-year performance review is arranged, sometimes it is found that few subordinates face difficulties to comprehend the issues in hand because of incapability which is addressed carefully by the management.

The major strength of performance management systems is that it is unbiased and the weakness is that very few executives find the opportunity of self-involvement.

Recommendation:

- a) Performance target must be clear, specific, interesting, challenging, time bound and linked with reward system.
- b) There should be more employee participation in the process.
- c) Appraisers must be trained. They should have knowledge about all factors on the basis of which performance is measured.
- d) Transparent feedback must be ensured.
- e) Review meetings must be direct and specific and must encourage the appraisers to talk carefully.
- f) Employees must be properly and adequately communicated regarding the assigning of values in terms of no. of performance.

Acknowledgement: We are thankful to the Hon'ble Chancellor, Al-Falah University, Dhauj, Faridabad (HR) for developing the infrastructure for research work in the Department of Management Studies, AFU, owing to which it has become possible to do the research work smoothly.

References:

1. Eleni T. Stavrou, Christakis Charalambous and Stelios Spiliotis, "Human resource management and performance: A neural network analysis", Elsevier Publications, European Journal of Operation Research, 181, (2007), 453-466.
2. Ya-Fen Tseng and Tzai-Zang Lee, "Comparing appropriate decision support of human resource practices on organizational performance with DEA/AHP model", Elsevier Publications, Expert Systems with Applications 36 (2009), 6548–6558.
3. W.-B. Lin, "The exploration of employee involvement model", Elsevier Publications, Expert Systems with Applications 31 (2006), 69-82.
4. Rachel W.Y.Yee, Andy C.L.Yeung and T.C.Edwin Cheng, "An empirical study of employee loyalty, service quality and firm performance in the service industry", Elsevier Publications, Int. J. Production Economics 124 (2010), 109–120.
5. Michael Workman, "A field study of corporate employee monitoring: Attitudes, absenteeism, and the moderating influences of procedural justice perceptions", Elsevier Publications, Information and Organization 19 (2009), 218–232.
6. Carolyn Holton, "Identifying disgruntled employee systems fraud risk through text mining: A simple solution for a multi-billion dollar problem", Elsevier Publications, Decision Support Systems 46 (2009), 853–864.
7. Nader Azizi, Saeed Zolfaghari and Ming Liang, "Modeling job rotation in manufacturing systems: The study of employee's boredom and skill variations", Elsevier Publications, Int. J. Production Economics 123 (2010), 69–85.
8. Julie M. Hays and Arthur V. Hill, "A preliminary investigation of the relationships between employee motivation/vision, service learning, and perceived service quality", Elsevier Publications, Journal of Operations Management 19 (2001), 335–349.
9. M.Sudan Taylor, Academy of Management Journal 1998 "Managers' Reactions To Procedurally Just Performance Management Systems" vol.41 pp 568-579
10. [2] Victor Y/.Haines, Candian Journal of Administrative Sciences 2004 " Performance Management Design And Effectiveness in Quality-Driven Organizations" vol.21 pp 146-161
11. Dr. A.Srinivasa Rao, the International Journal of Human Resource Management 2007 "Effectiveness Of Performance Management Systems" Indian School Of Business, Hyderabad
12. Adrian Furnham, European Business Journal 2004 "Performance Management Systems" Univesity College London, London

13. Kostas N.Dervitsiotis, Total Quality Management “*The Design of Performance Measurement Systems for Management Learning*” vol.15 No.4, pp 457-473, University of Piraeus, Greece
14. Performance Management and Appraisal Systems, T V Rao